

informed_consent

Participant Information Sheet and Informed Consent

We invite you to participate in this research study. Please take the time to read the following information carefully.

What is the purpose of this study?

We seek to study the public's opinion.

What will happen if I take part?

We will ask you to read five short statements and to give us your opinion about them. After that, we will ask you to evaluate five actors. Finally, we would like to know some details about yourself. Participation will take about 4 minutes.

Do I have to take part?

Your participation is entirely voluntary. You have the right to decline or withdraw participation at any point. If you choose to proceed, we expect you to be at least 18 years old and have read and understood this information sheet.

Will my participation be kept confidential?

We will not ask you to provide your name or any personally identifiable information. All data collected during this research project are anonymous and stored on secure, encrypted servers.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

We do not anticipate any risks to you.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

You will be compensated for your time if you complete all the tasks and answer all the questions.

How will my information be used?

Your information will solely be used as part of this study to answer questions about public perceptions. Any results or data resulting from this study will only be shared in a completely anonymized form.

Further information and contact details

This study is being conducted by #####.

Please get in touch with ##### for additional information.

Thank you for taking the time to read this document. By continuing you confirm that you have read and agreed with the terms in this information sheet.

Prolific ID

What is your Prolific ID?

Please note that this response should auto-fill with the correct ID

`#{e://Field/PROLIFIC_PID}`

exp_instructions

You will now be shown five claims. Please tell us how accurate you think they are on a scale from "not at all accurate" to "completely accurate".

imm_eco

Economists claim that immigration does not increase crime.

To the best of your knowledge, how accurate is the claim made above?

- Not at all accurate
- Not very accurate
- Somewhat accurate
- Very accurate
- Completely accurate

imm_soc

Sociologists claim that immigration does not increase crime.

To the best of your knowledge, how accurate is the claim made above?

- Not at all accurate
- Not very accurate
- Somewhat accurate
- Very accurate
- Completely accurate

imm_sci

Scientists claim that immigration does not increase crime.

To the best of your knowledge, how accurate is the claim made above?

- Not at all accurate
- Not very accurate
- Somewhat accurate
- Very accurate
- Completely accurate

imm_con

Immigration does not increase crime.

To the best of your knowledge, how accurate is the claim made above?

- Not at all accurate
- Not very accurate
- Somewhat accurate
- Very accurate
- Completely accurate

tax_eco

Economists claim that taxing the rich and corporations reduces government income.

To the best of your knowledge, how accurate is the claim made above?

- Not at all accurate
- Not very accurate
- Somewhat accurate
- Very accurate
- Completely accurate

tax_soc

Sociologists claim that taxing the rich and corporations reduces government income.

To the best of your knowledge, how accurate is the claim made above?

- Not at all accurate
- Not very accurate
- Somewhat accurate
- Very accurate
- Completely accurate

tax_sci

Scientists claim that taxing the rich and corporations reduces government income.

To the best of your knowledge, how accurate is the claim made above?

- Not at all accurate
- Not very accurate
- Somewhat accurate
- Very accurate
- Completely accurate

tax_con

Taxing the rich and corporations reduces government income.

To the best of your knowledge, how accurate is the claim made above?

- Not at all accurate
- Not very accurate
- Somewhat accurate
- Very accurate
- Completely accurate

gmo_agr

Agricultural scientists claim that genetically modified organisms do not harm peoples' health.

To the best of your knowledge, how accurate is the claim made above?

- Not at all accurate
- Not very accurate
- Somewhat accurate
- Very accurate
- Completely accurate

gmo_env

Environmental scientists claim that genetically modified organisms do not harm peoples' health.

To the best of your knowledge, how accurate is the claim made above?

- Not at all accurate
- Not very accurate
- Somewhat accurate
- Very accurate
- Completely accurate

gmo_sci

Scientists claim that genetically modified organisms do not harm peoples' health.

To the best of your knowledge, how accurate is the claim made above?

- Not at all accurate
- Not very accurate
- Somewhat accurate
- Very accurate
- Completely accurate

gmo_con

Genetically modified organisms do not harm peoples' health.

To the best of your knowledge, how accurate is the claim made above?

- Not at all accurate
- Not very accurate
- Somewhat accurate
- Very accurate
- Completely accurate

cli_agr

**Agricultural scientists claim that the Earth's climate is changing
because of human activity.**

To the best of your knowledge, how accurate is the claim made above?

- Not at all accurate
- Not very accurate
- Somewhat accurate
- Very accurate
- Completely accurate

cli_env

**Environmental scientists claim that the Earth's climate is changing
because of human activity.**

To the best of your knowledge, how accurate is the claim made above?

- Not at all accurate
- Not very accurate
- Somewhat accurate
- Very accurate
- Completely accurate

cli_sci

Scientists claim that the Earth's climate is changing because of human activity.

To the best of your knowledge, how accurate is the claim made above?

- Not at all accurate
- Not very accurate
- Somewhat accurate
- Very accurate
- Completely accurate

cli_con

The Earth's climate is changing because of human activity.

To the best of your knowledge, how accurate is the claim made above?

- Not at all accurate
- Not very accurate
- Somewhat accurate
- Very accurate
- Completely accurate

attention

This claim aims to show that you are paying attention.

To the best of your knowledge, can you please select somewhat accurate below?

- Not at all accurate
- Not very accurate
- Somewhat accurate
- Very accurate
- Completely accurate

trst_instructions

You will now read about five actors. Please tell us how much you trust them to perform certain tasks on a scale from "completely distrust" to "completely trust".

eco_trst

How much do you distrust or trust **economists** to ...

	Completely distrust	Partially distrust	Neither distrust nor trust	Partially trust	Completely trust
... create knowledge that is unbiased and accurate?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... create knowledge that is useful?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... advise government officials?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... inform the public on important issues?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

agr_trst

How much do you distrust or trust **agricultural scientists** to ...

	Completely distrust	Partially distrust	Neither distrust nor trust	Partially trust	Completely trust
... create knowledge that is unbiased and accurate?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... create knowledge that is useful?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... advise government officials?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... inform the public on important issues?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

soc_trst

How much do you distrust or trust **sociologists** to ...

	Completely distrust	Partially distrust	Neither distrust nor trust	Partially trust	Completely trust
... create knowledge that is unbiased and accurate?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... create knowledge that is useful?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... advise government officials?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... inform the public on important issues?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

env_trst

How much do you distrust or trust **environmental scientists** to ...

	Completely distrust	Partially distrust	Neither distrust nor trust	Partially trust	Completely trust
... create knowledge that is unbiased and accurate?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... create knowledge that is useful?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... advise government officials?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... inform the public on important issues?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

sci_trst

How much do you distrust or trust **scientists** to ...

	Completely distrust	Partially distrust	Neither distrust nor trust	Partially trust	Completely trust
... create knowledge that is unbiased and accurate?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... create knowledge that is useful?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... advise government officials?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... inform the public on important issues?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

cont_and_pol_vars

Please share some details about yourself.

How old are you?

Please choose the gender identity that best describes you.

- Male
- Female
- Non-binary
- None of these

What is the highest level of education you have completed?

- Less than high school
- High school graduate
- Some college
- College graduate
- Professional degree
- Postgraduate degree

Which of these topics do you believe are relevant for society? You may choose one or more.

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Taxation | <input type="checkbox"/> Gender equality |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Biodiversity | <input type="checkbox"/> Artificial intelligence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Genetically-modified organisms | <input type="checkbox"/> Nuclear energy production |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Foreign military assistance | <input type="checkbox"/> Immigration |

How much, if at all, do you trust the information you get from ...

	Not at all	Not too much	Some	A lot
Public television	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Private television	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Public radio	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Private radio	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Print publications	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
News websites or apps	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Social media sites or apps (e.g., Facebook, Twitter/X, Instagram, WhatsApp, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

In the two questions below, please choose the options that best describe you.

When it comes to politics, do you usually think of yourself as ...

- Extremely liberal
- Liberal
- Slightly liberal
- Moderate, middle of the road
- Slightly conservative
- Conservative
- Extremely conservative

Generally speaking, do you usually think of yourself as a ...

- Strong Democrat
- Moderate Democrat
- Leaning Democrat
- Leaning Republican
- Moderate Republican
- Strong Republican

debrief

Thank you for participating in our study.

The purpose of the study is to find out whether the source discipline of a scientific claim has an effect on the perceived accuracy of that claim. We also want to know if trust in scientific disciplines depends on political identification. All the information you provided will be anonymized. If you have any comments or questions, please contact ##### or #####.

The next screen will redirect you to the completion page on Prolific.

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